

RELIABILITY ANALYSIS OF ARAMID FIBRE YARNS

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SUMMARY

The creep rupture of aramid fibre yarns (Twaron 1000 and Kevlar 29) was studied experimentally at different temperatures. The failure stress and strain data were analyzed by statistical techniques. The reliability analysis, including extraction of Weibull parameters and distribution estimation, allows useful predictions for the long term creep rupture behaviour.

Keywords: Aramid, Creep, Reliability, Weibull parameters

INTRODUCTION

Aramid is the most remarkable high strength polymer fibre for its high thermal and mechanical properties. The use of aramid fibres in cables, pipes, belts, tyres and similar applications demands the knowledge of their behaviour when they are subjected to combined loadings for long periods of time. Research work over the last decades has reported results on the mechanical behaviour of different aramid fibres for different situations (tensile stress, creep, fatigue etc.).

It is widely accepted and confirmed by experimental studies that Poisson-Weibull probabilistic approach is the most suitable procedure to describe the ultimate mechanical behaviour of solids with linear stress-strain behaviour up to failure. The high variability in strength, due to various random flaws on the fibre surface and in the fibre interior, as found in brittle aramid fibres, was successfully modelled by Weibull-Poisson statistics [1-4]

The basis for probabilistic modelling of multi-filament bundles has been established by Weibull [1,2] in the form of the weakest-link model. The Weibull distribution concept was applied in the formulation of the fibre bundle models by Daniels [5] and Coleman [3,4]. The model proposed in 1958 by Coleman on phenomenological grounds was justified later by Phoenix and co-authors in its basic form.

Phoenix [6,7] reviewed the fibre bundles probabilistic models. In his approach the classical equal load sharing model is treated as a special case of the generalized model, where the load on each surviving fibre is not necessarily the same. In this way he extended the generalized models to some particular cases (elastic fibre bundles with random fibre slack and hybrid bundles with different types of fibres). Furthermore, using a modified kinematic hypothesis, Phoenix [8] extended the strain based bundle model to twisted yarn structures.

The conventional Weibull distribution was used satisfactory to describe the strength

behaviour of materials with random flaws [9-13]. Some weaknesses of the fibre bundle models using the Weibull distribution concept led to further research in order to develop new versions. Thus, Wagner et al. [14-16] modified and improved the model by taking into account the size effect (the fibre diameter influence). Wu et al. [17] reported on the temperature dependence of probabilistic models in creep rupture. He described the scale parameter of the lifetime distribution of Kevlar filaments, using the Arrhenius approach and the activation energies. Phoenix and Wu [18] used silicone–oil lubricant to reduce the friction between the fibres. Other results using statistical and probabilistic techniques for the study of aramid bundles or yarns were published recently [19-23].

In previous research [24] creep and stress rupture of two types of aramid fibre yarns (Twaron 1000 and Kevlar 29) were investigated. An extrapolation of the ISO 9080 procedure (developed for thermoplastic pipe materials) was used to model the results. The 4 parameter model fitted well the results and provided a good description for the long term stress and creep rupture. Since the investigation was made on twisted yarns, where the strength statistical variation is partially eliminated, the variability of the results was not analyzed. In order to validate the previous 4 parameter models based on the ISO 9080 procedure and the conclusions on the long term behaviour of aramid fibre yarns, we considered it necessary to extend the research and to perform a reliability analysis of the experimental data. The present paper reports the results of the reliability analysis, by statistical techniques, including extraction of Weibull parameters and distribution estimation.

THEORETICAL FUNDAMENTALS

Weibull distribution represents the most basic modelling tool used in reliability analyses to predict failure rates and to provide a description of the failure behaviour of structures and systems. Considering factors such as anisotropy, internal structure, stresses and influence of environment, the specific strength value of composite materials is difficult to be defined in each situation. For this reason, the Weibull distribution is often used to model the fracture strength of composite materials. The Weibull distribution is characterized by ‘shape’ and ‘scale’ parameters.

The high variability in brittle fibres properties can be well modelled by Weibull-Poisson statistics. Thus, for aramid fibres, the probability of failure can be expressed by the two parameters *Weibull cumulative distribution function*:

$$P_{(\varepsilon)} = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_0} \right)^m \right] \quad 0 \leq P_{(\varepsilon)} \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

where ε is the applied strain, ε_0 is the Weibull scale parameter and m the Weibull shape parameter.

As follows, if taking into account the length influence, the reliability of aramid fibres can be defined by the *Weibull survival function*:

$$S_{(\varepsilon)} = \exp \left[- \left(\frac{L}{L_0} \right)^\nu \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_0} \right)^m \right] \quad 0 \leq S_{(\varepsilon)} \leq 1 \quad (2)$$

where L is the yarn length, L_0 is the reference length and ν the adjustment for non-

Weibull effects.

The parameters m and ε_0 are estimated from observations. The usual methods used in the estimation of these parameters are the method of maximum likelihood estimation (ML), method of least squares (LS) and method of moments.

At the same time, creep rupture of aramid fibre is sensitive to environmental and testing conditions (humidity, temperature, stress level etc.). The creep rate of fibres can be accelerated by changing these parameters. However, most of the creep rupture models have been based on tests carried out at room temperature and at high stress levels, when creep failures occurs in days or, even, in hours. For long term loadings, when lifetimes of more than 20 years can be expected, significant extrapolations are needed. Some results using these extrapolation techniques, such as the ISO 9080 procedure [24] or TTSP (Time Temperature Superposition Principle) [25], were already reported.

Standards and qualification procedures for reinforced thermoplastic pipes invariably use the power law model rather than Eyring, although in most cases each would fit the results equally well. The reason for preferring the power law model is simple: extrapolation of failure data assumed to be linear in log–log space gives a slightly more favourable life prediction than the equivalent extrapolation in lin–log space.

Since for reinforced thermoplastic pipes, fibre failure is the key failure mechanism, the aramid yarns are also assumed to behave in the same way, so the following relationship was assumed [24] between the applied stress s and the time to failure t_f :

$$\sigma = Ft_f^{-G} \quad (3)$$

so the equation of the stress rupture curve is

$$\log \sigma = \log F - G \log t_f \quad (4)$$

where F and G are power law constants ($-G$ being the regression line slope). Alternatively, in terms of time to failure:

$$t_f = \left(\frac{F}{\sigma} \right)^{\frac{1}{G}} \quad (5)$$

As aramid fibres remain crystalline at all temperatures, the relationship between the temperature and the horizontal shift factor is based on the Arrhenius equation. Thus, assuming the Arrhenius dependence, for the applied stress σ , the time to failure equation can be amended to:

$$t_f = A \cdot \exp\left(\frac{\Delta H}{RT}\right) \sigma^{-\frac{1}{G}} \quad (6)$$

where ΔH is the activation energy of the process, R is the universal gas constant, T is the absolute temperature.

ISO 9080 [26], which was developed for thermoplastic pipes, offers a useful procedure and extrapolation protocol for modelling stress failure data. The same approach has been recommended for modelling other types of failure data. ISO 9080 assumes that the time to failure is given by an expression of the form:

$$\log(t_f) = c_1 + \frac{c_2}{T} + c_3 \log(\sigma) + \frac{c_4 \log(\sigma)}{T} \quad (7)$$

where c_1 , c_2 , c_3 and c_4 are fitting constants and T is the absolute temperature. Comparing this with equation (6) it can be seen that the constants are related by

$$\begin{aligned} \log A &= c_1 \\ \Delta H &= 2.302585kc_2 \\ G &= -\frac{1}{c_3 + \frac{c_4}{T}} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Finally:

$$\log F = \frac{-c_1 - \frac{c_2}{T}}{c_3 + \frac{c_4}{T}} \quad (9)$$

Beside the 4 parameter model, a simplified version, the 3 parameter model (considering $c_4=0$), is available within the procedure. Calculation procedures for the least squares fit and the statistical lower prediction limit are explained in ISO 9080 [26] and will not therefore be discussed here.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Aramid fibre yarns Twaron 1000 (1680 dtex) and Kevlar 29 (1670 dtex), supplied by Teijin and DuPont respectively were studied. Both yarns were supplied with the same twist level of 'z80' (i80 turns per metre). Creep rupture tests at constant load, in air, at 25, 65, 95 and 120°C were performed [24] using specifically designed temperature controlled dead loading rigs, as in Fig. 1. Also, a computer controlled mechanical testing machine equipped with a temperature controlled oven was used in constant load mode for a number of short term tests. Some further experiments to measure creep strain were carried out at two temperatures, 25 and 65°C, using a linear voltage differential transformer (LVDT). More detailed experimental conditions and technical data are presented in the previous report [24].

Figure 1. Schematic of stress rupture testing equipment

The principal aim was to establish values of the regression line gradient and 20 year

design parameters for the fibre yarns, especially at the most frequently used design temperature of 65°C. A secondary aim was to look for evidence of any long term changes in failure mode that would affect the suitability of the fibre for long term use.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Failure stress experimental results and the 4 parameter models for the two different yarns are presented in Fig. 2. [24]. The ISO 9080 was effective in correlating the behaviour at different times and temperatures.

Figure 2. Experimental data and ISO 9080 4 parameter models for Twaron 1000 and Kevlar 29 yarns

Figure 3 [24] shows the measured creep strains, at 25 and 65°C respectively. The general features are a rapid, mainly elastic response, followed by a low rate of creep deformation. It does appear that a short relaxation process may take place in the first minutes after loading, as it takes some minutes for the curves to level out. After this, the creep rate, per decade appears to be almost constant. A constant creep rate in linear time, which is observed with many materials in the secondary stage of creep, would imply an upwardly curving creep response in logarithmic time, which does not appear to occur in the present case. This, of course, implies the existence of some ‘hardening’ process, as the creep rate is, in effect slowing down with time. The creep rate per decade appears to be heavily dependent of stress, as it reduces to a very low rate for stresses that would cause failure at times of 10 h and beyond.

Figure 3. Creep behaviour of aramid yarn at 25 and 65°C, for different stress levels

Comparing to the untwisted fibres, where a Weibull analysis of the results would be required, it was assumed that twisted yarns largely eliminate the strength variability by allowing stress to be shared, through friction, between adjacent filaments when a particular filament fails. Since in the previous work [24] the tested yarns were twisted with the twist level of ‘z80’ (i80 turns per metre), a Weibull analysis was not performed.

However, quite a large scatter of experimental data was observed, especially for the creep strain. For this reason, a reliability analysis of the creep and stress failure data was considered necessary.

Experimental data for the failure time were fitted to different distributions (normal, lognormal, Weibull, 3 parameter Weibull etc.). Basic statistics were extracted for each distribution. Two goodness-of-fit statistical methods were used to estimate and compare the fit of the distributions:

- The maximum likelihood (ML) method, using the Anderson-Darling statistic (AD*);
- The least squares (LS) method, using the Pearson correlation coefficient.

The comparison of best fitted models with the ML and LS estimates is presented in Fig. 4 (for Twaron 1000) and Fig. 5 (for Kevlar 29). For both materials, the statistical coefficients have comparable values for the Weibull, the 3 parameter Weibull, the lognormal and the 3 parameter lognormal distributions. Thus, it can be assumed that all these distributions could be used to describe the time to failure. However, for almost temperatures, the estimates seem to be slightly better for the 3 parameter lognormal distribution. As the 3 parameter lognormal model is the simplified version of the ISO 9080 4 parameter model, the result of the statistical comparison confirms and validates the previous models presented in Fig. 2.

Probability Plot for time to failure 25, 65, 95, 120 - TWARON 1000

Figure 4. Comparison of best fitted distributions for time to failure – TWARON 1000

Nevertheless, even if the variability of the results is partially reduced, compared with fibre filaments or fibre bundles, the Weibull distribution can be used to describe the

time to failure adequately. Fig. 6 and 7 show the empirical cumulative distribution function CDF for the Weibull distribution of time to failure of Twaron 1000 yarns and Kevlar 29 yarns, respectively. Weibull shape and scale parameters are extracted and presented in these figures.

Figure 5. Comparison of best fitted distributions for time to failure – KEVLAR 29

As expected, the shape parameter, m , increased with the temperature for both materials. This observation confirms that the temperature has an influence on the fibre yarns strength variability. This is similar to the fibre filaments or bundles, already reported. The extracted shape parameters show a higher influence of the temperature for the Twaron 1000 yarns (from 0.31 to 0.59) than for the Kevlar 29 yarns (from 0.29 to 0.44).

Empirical CDF of time to failure 25, 65, 95, 120 - TWARON 1000

Figure 6. Empirical CDF and Weibull parameters for time to failure – TWARON 1000

Empirical CDF of time to failure 25, 65, 95, 120 - KEVLAR 29

Figure 7. Empirical CDF and Weibull parameters for time to failure – KEVLAR 29

Using a similar statistical technique, measured creep strain was fitted for different distributions and the goodness-of-fit was estimated. Fig. 8 shows the results at 65°C for the Twaron 1000 yarns. The Weibull and the lognormal distribution best fit the experimental data. Estimates indicate that, unlike the time to failure data, the Weibull distribution best describes the creep strain for all stress levels considered.

Probability Plot for strain data - TWARON 1000

Anderson-Darling (adj.) Weibull	Correlation Coefficient Weibull
78.54, 48.13, 211.27, 18.45, 16.64, 1.60	0.878, 0.965, 0.873, 0.922, 0.870, 0.892
Lognormal	Lognormal
90.10, 58.20, 866.52, 40.61, 39.70, 9.05	0.767, 0.914, 0.760, 0.842, 0.750, 0.801

Figure 8. Comparison of best fitted distributions for creep strain – TWARON 1000

However, comparing the estimates of both distributions considered, the lognormal distribution can be accepted to characterize the creep strain in this case. Thus, even if the Weibull distribution seems slightly better, the statistical analysis confirms and validates the lognormal models found in the previous research as shown in Fig. 3. The cumulative distribution function CDF and the extracted Weibull parameters for the creep strain of Twaron 1000 yarns are shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 9. Empirical CDF and Weibull parameters for creep strain – TWARON 1000

The Weibull analysis offered useful information on the creep strain at different stress levels. The variability of the results was greater than expected for the yarns and confirms again that the effect of twisting the fibres cannot eliminate the strength variations in the aramid yarns completely. The different values of the shape parameter, m , for different stress levels cannot be compared in this case because of the great difference between the sample sizes in each situation.

CONCLUSIONS

Using statistical analysis, the experimental data were fitted to different distributions. Basic statistics were extracted for each distribution and the various distributions were compared. Weibull parameters were extracted from typical Weibull plots.

The reliability analysis offered important information regarding the strength of studied aramid fibre yarns. Also it proved to be a suitable technique to make predictions on the lifetime of aramid fibres. Some advantages of this statistical approach could be highlighted.

The creep rupture data were analyzed and used to characterize the long term failure behaviour of two different aramid fibre yarns. Both aramid yarns studied showed very similar behaviour. The time to failure of the aramid yarns is best represented by the 3 or 4 parameter lognormal model. Thus, the ISO 9080 procedure can be successfully

extrapolated to describe the failure of aramid fibre yarns. However, since the failure data have still a high degree of variability, the Weibull distribution describes the failure of the aramid fibre yarns quite well. This can be explained by the strength variation of aramid fibres, reduced, but not totally eliminated in the twisted yarns.

The variability is much higher for the creep strain data, the Weibull distribution being the most suitable to characterize it. As the lognormal distribution still describes the creep strain of the analyzed aramid fibre yarns quite accurately, it can be used to create prediction models as in the previous work.

At this point, no attempt to find any physical explanations for the results of the reliability analysis has been made. This paper was intended only to evaluate the statistical techniques that could be used to analyze stress rupture and creep strain data, in order to make extrapolations to achieve useful structural lifetime models.

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